

Tackling the problem of drugs of abuse sensing through nanomaterials and (bio)recognition approaches

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13 **Abstract**

14 We summarize herein the literature in the last decade, involving the use of nanomaterials and
15 various (bio)recognition elements, such as antibodies, aptamers and molecularly imprinted
16 polymers, for the development of sensitive and selective (bio)sensors for illicit drugs with a focus
17 on electrochemical transduction systems.

18 Illicit drugs use and abuse remains an increasing challenge for worldwide authorities and,
19 therefore, it is important to have accurate methods to detect them in seized samples, biological
20 fluids and wastewaters. They are recently classified as the latest group of ‘emerging pollutants’,
21 as their consumption increased tremendously in recent years.

22 Nanomaterials, antibodies, aptamers and molecularly imprinted polymers have gained much
23 attention over the last decade in the development of (bio)sensors for a myriad of applications. The
24 applicability of these (nano)materials, functionalized or not, significantly increases and are
25 therefore highly suitable for use in the detection of drugs of abuse. Lately, such functionalized
26 nanoscale materials have assisted in the detection of illicit drugs fingerprints, providing large
27 surface area, functional groups and unique properties that facilitate sensitive and selective sensing.

28 The review discusses about the types of drugs of abuse and their toxicological implications,
29 classification of functionalized nanomaterials (graphene, carbon nanotubes), their fabrication, and
30 their application on real samples in different fields of forensic science. Biosensors for drugs of
31 abuse from the last decade’s literature are then exemplified. It also offers insights into the prospects

32 and challenges of bringing the functionalized nano-based technology to the end user in the
33 laboratories or in-field.

34 **1 Introduction**

35 Despite the “war on drugs”, drug abuse is a major concern worldwide with devastating effects on
36 human health, economy and communities. Cannabis is one of the longest-established drugs in
37 Europe and is the most commonly used illicit drug, with nearly 20% of those in the 15-24 age
38 group reporting having used cannabis in the last year. In 2017, 1.1 million drug seizures were
39 reported in Europe. Herbal cannabis accounts to 42% of total number of drug seizures in 2017,
40 followed by cannabis resin with 28%. Cocaine is next on the list with 10%, followed by
41 amphetamines 5%, heroin 4% and MDMA 3% (European Monitoring Centre for Drugs and Drug
42 Addiction, 2019).

43 The current detection of illicit drugs in seized street samples is performed by quick, presumptive
44 tests, such as colour tests, however these tests lack selectivity, and need further confirmation by
45 expensive and time-consuming chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) methods.
46 Therefore, it is of interest to develop new sensing technologies that allow a fast, sensitive and
47 selective detection of illicit drugs in-the-field.

48 Electrochemical methods proved to be a great alternative for the fast determination of drugs with
49 high sensitivity and selectivity and are easy to miniaturize into portable devices to be used in-the-
50 field. Electrochemical detection of several illicit drugs has been reported in literature and proved
51 to be effective for accurately detecting illicit drugs in complex adulterated street samples (Florea
52 et al., 2019c). Nanomaterials and biomimetic platforms (e.g. aptamers, molecularly imprinted
53 polymers-MIP) have gained much attention over the last decade in the development of (bio)sensors
54 for a myriad of applications. The applicability of these (nano)materials makes them highly suitable
55 for use in the detection of drugs of abuse. Lately, (functionalized) nanomaterials have assisted in
56 the detection of illicit drugs fingerprints, providing large surface area, rich functional groups and
57 unique properties that facilitate sensitive and selective sensing (Rawtani et al., 2019).

58 Current drug measurements in body fluids, such as blood, urine and saliva, are performed by
59 centralized laboratories using classical methods and bulky instruments based on liquid
60 chromatography, GC-MS and GC-MS with solid phase micro-extraction (Purschke et al., 2016).
61 Electrochemical methods are also suitable for the detection of drugs of abuse in complex matrices
62 such as body fluids. Since drugs are present in low concentrations in body fluids the integration of
63 nanomaterials in electrochemical sensors is advantageous. Saliva-based drug detection is of
64 particular interest for on-site screening, as it is a non-invasive method, and unlike blood assays,
65 doesn't need invasive sample collection (Huestis and Smith, 2018). Most drugs degrade to their
66 metabolites and are therefore found along with their metabolites in body fluids. Sometimes special
67 attention in handling these samples is required. For example, heroin degrades to 6-
68 monoacetylmorphine and morphine *in vitro* and *in vivo*. *In vitro* the degradation is also dependent
69 on the pH and temperature. Analytical methods that include quantification of heroin recognize that
70 heroin and 6-monoacetylmorphine are unstable in certain matrices and suggest using freshly
71 prepared solutions (Jones et al., 2013).

72 This review focuses on recent development of (bio)sensors for the detection of drugs of abuse in
73 seized street samples and biological fluids. Given the importance of drug metabolites for the
74 detection in body fluids aspects regarding pharmacokinetics and toxicology of common drugs of
75 abuse are briefly discussed. The integration of nanomaterials and affinity elements, such as
76 aptamers and MIP into the sensors for increased sensitivity and selectivity is presented. Finally,
77 further improvements and the necessity to tackle the problem of selective detection are discussed.

78

79 **2 Types of drugs of abuse and their toxicological implications**

80 An overall increase in drug-related deaths has been observed over the last 5 years, with increases
81 reported in all age groups above the age of 30 years. Drug overdose deaths are rarely associated
82 with the consumption of one substance alone. Modern drug consumption patterns are highly
83 dynamic, with an increased number of drugs appearing on the market (European Monitoring
84 Centre for Drugs and Drug Addiction, 2019).

85 According to the European Drug Report 2019 cannabis is the most used drug with 24.7 million
86 users aged 15-64 in 2018 (European Monitoring Centre for Drugs and Drug Addiction, 2019). Δ^9 -
87 tetrahydrocannabinol (Δ -THC) is the compound responsible for the psychoactive actions of the
88 drug. Besides Δ^9 -THC, organic cannabis products contain additional cannabinoids which do not
89 produce psychoactive effects, such as cannabiol, and cannabidiol (Rhee et al., 1997; Pertwee,
90 2005). Synthetic cannabinoids are compounds prepared by chemical synthesis to produce the same
91 effects as Δ^9 -THC and have emerged more and more recently. They are more unsafe, as their
92 effects are more potent, and they also contain unknown chemicals made-up with the drug that may
93 have negative effects on human health. Δ^9 -THC metabolite, THC-COOH, can be detected in body
94 fluids, such as saliva, urine and blood, three to six hours after its consumption and can be retained
95 in the body for several days (Huestis, 2007). Detection in saliva would be preferred, as it is non-
96 invasive and simple compared to detection in blood. The concentration of Δ^9 -THC in saliva is a
97 function of the time since the cannabis consumption (Dobri et al., 2019), with a maximum salivary
98 Δ^9 -THC level of $16 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ observed 1-2 hours after consuming the drug (Niedbala et al., 2001).
99 Acute cannabis intoxication is associated with impaired driving, significantly increasing the odds
100 of motor vehicle collision (Dahlgren et al., 2020). The use of cannabis is associated with
101 pathological and behavioural toxicity (Huestis, 2007). Effects of short-term use include impaired
102 short-term memory, altered attention, hallucinations and distortions of spatial perception, anxiety,
103 bronchodilatation, palpitations, increased heart rate, nausea and appetite change (Volkow et al.,
104 2014; Cohen and Weinstein, 2018). Chronic effects of cannabis and cannabinoids use include long-
105 lasting cognitive impairments and a risk for developing mental disorders (anxiety, depression,
106 bipolar disorder, schizophrenia) (Degenhardt and Hall, 2008; Volkow et al., 2014; Cohen and
107 Weinstein, 2018).

108 Cocaine is the second most prevalent illicit drug with 3.9 million users in 2018 and an increasing
109 number and volume of seizures. Cocaine is a stimulant type drug which appears as white powder,
110 paste or rock-like and is often adulterated with compounds with similar effects, e.g. procaine,
111 having anaesthetic effects like cocaine, or diluted with non-active compounds, e.g. starch, glucose,

112 talcum. Cocaine is used by smoking, snorting or injecting, for effects of euphoria, elevated mood
113 and increased energy.

114 Cocaine is metabolized mainly to benzoylecgonine and in lesser amounts to ecgonine methyl ester,
115 as well as to norcocaine, p-hydroxycocaine, m-hydroxycocaine, p-hydroxybenzoylecgonine and
116 m-hydroxybenzoylecgonine. The detailed main mechanism is presented in **Figure 1** (Baciu et al.,
117 2015).

118 **Insert Figure 1**

119 Cocaine and its metabolites can be detected in body fluids such as saliva, urine and blood, and are
120 accumulated in hair. Urine testing is common for monitoring cocaine users in drug treatment. Peak
121 urine cocaine concentrations after snorting is of 300 to 24,000 ng mL⁻¹ in less than 1 h, while peak
122 urine benzoylecgonine (a metabolite of cocaine) concentrations ranged from 8100 to 70800 ng mL⁻¹
123 ¹ after of 4 to 8 h (Huestis et al., 2007). Cocaine concentration in hair is ≥ 0.5 ng mg⁻¹, while
124 benzoylecgonine concentration reaches ≥ 0.05 ng mg⁻¹. Acute effects of cocaine use include
125 increased heart rate and blood pressure, nausea and appetite change, vertigo and tremor. Chronic
126 use leads to severe constant fatigue, problems with memory, attention, strong headaches, severe
127 weight loss, motor and sexual dysfunction (Louis L. Cregler, 1988) .

128 Amphetamine type stimulants are a class of drugs mainly referring to amphetamine and
129 methamphetamine, but other drugs are also included in this group such as
130 methylenedioxymethamphetamine (MDMA) (ecstasy), 3,4-methylenedioxy-N-ethylamphetamine
131 (MDEA), methcathinone or ephedrine. As the name suggests this type of drugs has stimulant
132 effects on the nervous system. MDMA is the third most prevalent drug of abuse with 2.6 million
133 users in 2018, while amphetamine is the fourth most used with 1.7 million users in 2018 (European
134 Monitoring Centre for Drugs and Drug Addiction, 2019). Amphetamine type stimulants have been
135 used as medicines for the stimulant and appetite reducing effects and are still used today to treat
136 narcolepsy or attention deficit disorder. Short-term use effects include agitation, alertness, anxiety,
137 increased breath and heart rate, stomach pain, dilated pupils and blurred vision. Long term use
138 include sleeping problems, depression and chronic anxiety, poor memory, high blood pressure,
139 severe weight loss and risk of lung diseases (Heal et al., 2013; Cao et al., 2016; Haj-Mirzaian et
140 al., 2018).

141 Despite the decreasing use in Europe in the last year, as well as the decrease of HIV cases
142 associated with injecting heroin, opioids' use continues to make a major contribution to the health
143 and social costs in Europe, and the threats posed by this class of drug may even be growing. The
144 Drug Report 2019 accounts 1.3 million high-risk opioid users (European Monitoring Centre for
145 Drugs and Drug Addiction, 2019). Among the most used opioids currently are synthetic opioids,
146 particularly fentanyl derivatives. For example, carfentanyl is a very potent opioid that leads to
147 severe poisoning and deaths, which is trafficked in very small amounts making it difficult to detect.
148 An increasing role is played also by synthetic opioids that are usually used as medicines for e.g.
149 pain relief. When it comes to seizures, heroin is the most common opioid drug on the European
150 market. Heroin appears as a white powder and can be mixed with other white powders to dilute
151 the sample such as paracetamol, quinine, sugars or powdered milk. Adulterated heroin samples
152 appear as white to yellowish or brownish color. Black tar is another form of heroin which appears
153 as a black sticky- or coal-like substance. Regarding heroin pharmacokinetics, heroin degrades

154 rapidly to 6-monoacetylmorphine and morphine *in vivo* and *in vitro*, thus when analyzed in body
155 fluids this should be taken into consideration. Heroin and 6-monoacetylmorphine are found in
156 saliva 2 min after smoke or intravenous administration. The levels in body fluids of heroine
157 metabolites, morphine and 6-monoacetylmorphine, are in the nM range. The rate of degradation
158 depends on the type of biological sample and the duration and conditions of storage. The
159 degradation *in vitro* is also dependent on the pH and temperature (Jones et al., 2013). Acute effects
160 of heroin consumption include “rush” of pleasurable feelings followed by flushing of the skin,
161 reduced breathing and heart rate and severe itching. Chronic use may cause inflammation of the
162 gums, decreased memory and intellectual capacity, insomnia, impotence, infection of the blood
163 vessels, muscle weakness and pain and strong physical dependence and tolerance (Jones et al.,
164 2013).

165 **3. Examples of (bio)sensors for drugs of abuse**

166 Nowadays, (bio)sensors are widely used in biomedical diagnosis, point-of-care monitoring of
167 treatment and disease progression, but also in other areas such as environmental monitoring, food
168 control, drug discovery, forensics and biomedical research. Usually (bio)sensors are coupled with
169 high-affinity biomolecules or other recognition elements, such as molecularly imprinted polymers,
170 and in this way can allow the sensitive and selective detection of a high range of analytes. A typical
171 (bio)sensor is represented in **Figure 2**. A (bio)sensor is composed from the following units: an
172 analyte (the substance of interest), a (bio)receptor (a molecule that specifically recognizes the
173 analyte), a transducer (an element that converts one form of energy into another), electronics
174 (processes the transducer signal and prepares it for display) and a display (Bhalla et al., 2016). The
175 advantages of (bio)sensing systems are the possibility of miniaturization and automation, easy
176 fabrication and modification, low cost, and sensitivity.

177 **Insert Figure 2**

178 Our review provides the most relevant improvements and innovations in sensors and biosensors
179 development for the analysis of a range of commonly-encountered illicit substances in different
180 types of matrix, such as seized materials, biological and environmental samples. The targets we
181 selected refer to stimulants, such as amphetamine type drugs, cathinone and cocaine, depressants,
182 such as opium-related compounds and cannabinoids.

183 The most relevant studies in the literature of the lasts ten years about (bio)sensors developments
184 are summarized in Table 1.

185 **Insert Table 1.**

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3.1.Narcotics

191 Morphine (MO) is a narcotic and a pain-relieving drug, is a highly effective and preferred drug for
192 moderate treatment of severe pain. Two compounds with different structures result following the
193 morphine oxidation process, as can be seen in **Figure 3**. The first one is related to oxidation of
194 phenolic group, forming pseudomorphine. The second reaction is related to oxidation of the
195 tertiary amine group (Navaee et al., 2012).

196 **Insert Figure 3**

197 Rapid and simultaneous determination of morphine (MO) in pharmaceutical and illicit samples
198 has remained a great challenge in analytical chemistry. Electrochemical methods, especially
199 voltammetric methods, have been extensively used for opiates detection because these methods
200 are simple and provide improved selectivity (Atta et al., 2014). A novel ionic liquid modified
201 NiO/CNTs carbon paste electrode (IL/NiO/CNTCPE) was investigated by Sanati *et al.* using
202 square wave voltammetry. This sensing platform had been fabricated by using hydrophilic ionic
203 liquid 1-methyl-3-butylimidazolium chloride as a binder. After the functionalization, these
204 electrodes exhibited a potent and persistent electron mediating behaviour and a good peak-to-peak
205 separation of MO and diclofenac. In this case the detection limit was $0.01 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$. Successful
206 tests were performed in both human urine and pharmaceutical samples with good results (Sanati
207 et al., 2014).

208

3.2.Stimulants

209 Cocaine, an alkaloid extracted from *Erythroxylum coca plant*, is one of the most powerful
210 addictive stimulants that affect especially the brain. It is well known that cocaine is commonly
211 sold containing several other substances. Accurate drug detection is of utmost importance for
212 fighting against drug abuse. These substances are intentionally added to mimic the effects, to dilute
213 the active drug and increase the profits (Fiorentin et al., 2019). The adulterants and cutting agents
214 detection is usually quantified using spectrophotometric or chromatographic methods, which
215 involve high cost instrumentation and impossibilities for on-site detection (Freitas et al., 2017).
216 Recently, the use of electrochemical methods for the detection of adulterants or cutting agents has
217 been reported. For example, in a study developed by L. Asturias-Arribas *et al.*, it was shown that
218 by modification of disposable carbon sensors with carbon nanotubes cocaine can be detected in
219 the same sample with codeine, paracetamol or caffeine without any signal influences (Asturias-
220 Arribas et al., 2014). In another case, Freitas *et.al.* implemented a sensor for cocaine detection in
221 the presence of benzocaine, caffeine, lidocaine, phenacetine, paracetamol and procaine from a
222 seized sample through a bath-injection analysis system and with square-wave voltammetry.
223 Cocaine and the cutting agents were electrochemically oxidized on a boron-doped diamond
224 electrode (BDDE), resulting in a unique voltammetric profile (Freitas et al., 2017). It was also
225 discovered by Florea *et al.* a new method for the detection of cocaine in the presence of adulterant
226 levamisole on a graphite-based SPE platform through a polymer electrodeposition process (**Figure**
227 **4**). Aminobenzoic acid and *o*-phenylene diamine were electrodeposited onto graphite SPE. This
228 aided to avoid the adsorbition of levamisole onto the electrodes which leads to a suppression of
229 cocaine signal, allowing the simultaneous detection of both cocaine and levamisole (Florea et al.,
230 2018a).

231 **Insert Figure 4**

232 Another established class of stimulants is represented by cathinone. The most important synthetic
233 cathinone-based “legal highs” are methcathinone and its derivate, mephedrone, which are
234 structurally related to the natural stimulant, cathinone and possesses a pharmacological similarity
235 to the phenethylamine class of psychoactives (Smith et al., 2013). For cathinone detection a
236 disposable simultaneous electrochemical sensor array based on MIF (molecularly imprinted film)
237 with a SPE has been developed by Zang *et al.* For the MIF implementation, methcathinone and
238 cathinone were used as templates and pyrrole as the monomer. MIF was synthesized by electro-
239 polymerization. Through the NH_2 -graphene (NG) the conductivity of the SPE was improved.
240 Thus, with these modifications, the limits of detection for methcathinone and cathinone were going
241 down to 0.02 and 0.059 $nmol mL^{-1}$ respectively. Tests in serum sample were also performed
242 proving the potential of the sensor for clinical applications (Zang et al., 2013). Limits of detection
243 for cathinones determined in live and post-mortem whole blood samples is presented in Table 2.
244 These are important to keep in mind when developing sensors for the detection of cathinones in
245 blood samples.

246 **Insert Error! Reference source not found.2** (Sørensen, 2011)

247 The amphetamine-type stimulants (ATSS) are an important drug group and mainly contain
248 amphetamine and methamphetamine. Aside from this, other compounds are included in this class,
249 such as fenethylline, ephedrine, pseudoephedrine, methylphenidate, and 3,4-
250 methylenedioxymethamphetamine. Globally, the ATSS consumption is growing every day, so
251 sensitive and sensible analytical methods for their detection are needed. Narang *et al.* reported an
252 electrochemical analytical device (EPAD) for detection of MDMA who are mainly use as a
253 recreational drug. The working electrode of EPAD contains zinc oxid nanorods (ZnONRs). Tests
254 were performed at pH 7 in a concentration range between 1 $\mu mol L^{-1}$ and 1000 $\mu mol L^{-1}$ with a
255 detection limit of 0.1 $\mu mol L^{-1}$ for MDMA (Narang et al., 2018). In another approach Cumba *et*
256 *al.* developed a protocol for simultaneous detection of MDMA and para-methoxyamphetamine
257 (PMA) who are usually found in the same sample under the alias “ecstasy”, a very popular drug
258 of abuse. They used SPEs as such and obtained a detection limit of 1.295 $\mu mol L^{-1}$ / 0.227 μmol
259 mL^{-1} for MDMA/PMA, 0.207 $\mu mol L^{-1}$ for MDMA and 0.048 $\mu mol L^{-1}$ for PMA (Cumba et al.,
260 2016).

261 3.3.Cannabinoids

262 Balbino *et al.* discovered a new voltammetric method for Δ^9 -THC detection that was successfully
263 applied also for target analyte detection from seized samples. This approach was performed in N-
264 N dimethylformamide/water (9:1 V/V), using 0.1 $mol L^{-1}$ tetrabutylammonium tetrafluoroborate
265 (TBATFB) 0.1 $mol L^{-1}$ as supporting electrolyte and a glassy carbon disk as the working electrode.
266 Δ^9 -THC was successfully detected in a range between 0.0076 and 0.0359 $\mu mol L^{-1}$ with a detection
267 limit of 0.0001 $\mu mol L^{-1}$ (Balbino et al., 2012).

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271 4. Nanomaterials for sensors design for the detection of drugs of abuse

272 4.1. Graphene and graphene derivatives

273 Since 2004, graphene became the center piece of scientific research for exhaustive domains at the
274 moment it was synthesized by exfoliation of carbon by Geim and Novoselov (Geim and
275 Novoselov, 2007). Graphene is a 2D carbon-based nanomaterial with a single layer of sp^2
276 hybridized carbon atoms and the distance between two carbon atoms is approximately 1.42 Å.
277 It represents the basic element point in the synthesis of carbon nanotubes and fullerenes. It has a
278 large surface area ($2630 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$, twice as high as that of single-walled carbon nanotubes CNTs),
279 high conductivity, good chemical stability and mechanical strength. Graphene has an electron-rich
280 π -surface, that enables interaction with targeted analytes via van der Waals forces, charge transfer,
281 and π - π interactions (Meng et al., 2019).

282 The sp^2 hybridized carbon atoms network can be disrupted by the oxygen containing groups such
283 as carboxyls, epoxides and hydroxyls found in graphene oxide (GO). GO can differentiate between
284 the voltammograms of the drugs due to their high electrochemical conductivity and sensitivity
285 allowing simultaneous detection (de Araujo et al., 2018; Panwar et al., 2019; Rawtani et al., 2019).
286 The outstanding electrical properties of graphene can be restored by reduction via different
287 methods such as thermal, chemical or electrical strategies that result in a material with a high
288 amount of C-O bonds known as reduced GO (RGO). (Fakhari et al., 2014).

289 During the last decade it was used either as pristine graphene or in other forms such as GO, RGO,
290 chemically functionalized or not for the development of electrochemical (bio)sensors. The major
291 reason is that it is often included in various platforms for an enhanced sensitivity of detection by
292 generating an enlarged surface area and electron transfer rate that amplify the detection signal and
293 analytical performances of the (bio)sensor (Cernat et al., 2015, 2016; Beluomini et al., 2019). The
294 surface of graphene interacts with different analytes *via* van der Waals interactions, electron
295 transfer and covalent bonds depending on the functionalities found on the carbon-based material.

296 The fact that graphenes are commercially available at a reasonable price, the ease of dispersion in
297 aqueous environment and the facile electrochemical treatments are key assets of the material. All
298 the properties described above favor the development of portable electrochemical sensors suitable
299 for decentralized assays that were already reported for biomedical molecules and drug of abuse.
300 The (screen) printed electrodes (SPE) based on graphite or even graphene conductive inks enabled
301 fast adsorption kinetics, selectivity and a large binding capacity and in some case even reusability
302 (Couto et al., 2016). In this case the sensor is prepared via a simple method: (1) the deposition of
303 the modifier by drop coating on the graphite-based working surface (graphene, carbon nanotubes
304 (CNT) or fullerenes/metallic nanoparticles (NPs)/polymeric films or (bio)recognition sites, (2) the
305 addition of the sample on the modified electrode and (3) the electrochemical assessment by
306 differential pulse voltammetry (DPV) or square wave voltammetry (SWV) methods that can be
307 easily implemented on a miniaturized potentiostat.

308 Starting from graphene nanosheets the morphologies and functionalities became more
309 sophisticated to keep up with the requirements of biomedical/forensic applications regarding the
310 analytical performances.

311 4.2. Electrochemical sensors for drugs of abuse detection based on graphene

312 Graphene nanosheets deposited on glassy carbon electrodes (GCE) were employed for the
313 detection of morphine, heroin and noscapine by DPV, individually, in binary combinations or
314 simultaneously. The presence of graphene allowed the detection of the three opiates at reduced
315 overpotentials at micromolar concentration with no pretreatment steps (Navaee et al., 2012).
316 Electrochemically exfoliated GO has conductive properties even in the absence of an
317 electrochemical reduction protocol due to the presence of a higher density of oxidized moieties.
318 The material allowed the detection of morphine with a limit of detection (LOD) of 0.0025 mg L^{-1}
319 with a paper-based sensor suitable for the detection of the molecule in real case scenarios
320 (Maccaferri et al., 2019a).

321 Additionally, graphene bearing amino groups were used as a support for the elaboration of a MIP
322 sensor for the detection of methcathinone and cathinone using polypyrrole as monomer. In this
323 case the role of the carbon-based material was to ensure the substrate for the MIP by enhancing
324 the active surface area and the conductivity of the working surface of the graphite printed electrode.
325 This configuration allowed the detection of methcathinone with a LOD of 3.3 pg mL^{-1} and
326 cathinone with a LOD of 8.9 pg mL^{-1} (Zang et al., 2013). The synthesis of graphene hybrid
327 materials using metallic NPs represents a strategy to improve the electrocatalytical properties of
328 the new platforms. The fast electron transfer between the electrochemical species from the sample
329 and the composite nanomaterial generally results in an amplification of the signal. A positive
330 aspect relies in the large surface of graphene that allows the homogenous deposition of the NPs
331 with a low risk of aggregation. Reduced GO (RGO) and PdNPs generated a hybrid material
332 synthesized *via* microwave irradiation that showed superior catalytical properties towards the
333 electrochemical oxidation of morphine as in the presence of unmodified RGO. The sensor had a
334 LOD of $12.95 \text{ nmol L}^{-1}$. This fact highlights the effect of Pd on the sensitivity of the method and
335 the discrimination of the electrochemical signal of the target in the presence of other electroactive
336 species commonly found in biological samples such as dopamine, ascorbic and uric acid (Atta et
337 al., 2014). The association between AuNPs and graphene were an extensively studied approach
338 during the last decade due to the enhancement in the electron transfer rate, an important feature in
339 the development of electrochemical sensors. In this case, AuNPs act as a stimulator to improve the
340 electron transfer with GO improving reaction kinetics considerably compared to pristine GO
341 material (Kumar et al., 2018). The composite platform acted as the support for an aptamer-based
342 sandwich that allowed the detection of cocaine at nanomolar level, a real advantage for the
343 assessment of real samples (Jiang et al., 2012).. In another approach, Maccaferri *et al.* developed
344 a graphene oxide modified screen-printed electrode (GO-SPE) as amperometric sensor for MO
345 determination. By using this platform, they have obtained a higher sensitivity and a limit of
346 detection of $8.77 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ } \mu\text{mol mL}^{-1}$. They also have discovered that, the electrocatalytic coating is
347 necessary as modifier for the carbon electrode, for resolving the oxidation peak due to MO
348 oxidation despite to uric acid one (Maccaferri et al., 2019b).

349 Graphene can also be made magnetic. Molecular devices, controlled via magnetic forces, have
350 many applications in the development of bioelectronic for biomedical assays. Iron oxide, either
351 Fe_3O_4 or Fe_2O_3 , represents a magnetic nanomaterial with good biocompatibility, low toxicity and
352 stability, properties that recommend it for the development of (bio)sensors in association with
353 other carbon-based nanomaterials. Magnetic graphene yielded high conductivity, surface-to-

354 volume ratio and magnetocrystalline anisotropy. After the functionalization of this new 2D
355 material with labeled aptamers for cocaine and adenosine triphosphate, the platform allowed the
356 detection of analytes within picomolar range. The electrical contact between the biomolecules and
357 the working surface was made with an external magnet that immobilized it on the surface of the
358 transducers (Tang et al., 2011). Similarly, magnetic RGO in association with polyaniline and
359 AuNPs generated a hybrid platform that was further functionalized with a cocaine aptamer. The
360 impedimetric sensor allowed the detection of cocaine from 0.09 to 85 nmol L^{-1} with a LOD of
361 0.029 nmol L^{-1} with satisfactory detection from real samples even in the presence of other
362 commonly found compounds such as heroin and caffeine. Magnetic RGO has an increased surface
363 area and facilitates the electron transfer rate, while the presence of the conductive polymer
364 enhances the stability and conductivity of the platform in general by the presence of hydrophilic
365 groups. The catalytic properties are also increased by AuNPs (Hashemi et al., 2017).

366 **4.3. Carbon nanotubes**

367 **4.3.1. Properties of carbon nanotubes important for sensors**

368 Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) represent a very special category of carbon nanomaterials discovered
369 in 1991 by Iijima (Iijima, 1991), and which quickly became one of the most popular research
370 topics, especially in the field of sensors. This fact is mainly due to their special properties such as
371 increased surface area, high thermal stability, electric conductivity and mechanical strength, as
372 well as their easy and simple functionalization and modification with inorganic and organic
373 compounds or functions.

374 The intensive use of CNT as electrode surface modifiers is due to their electrocatalytic activity,
375 efficient promotion of charge transfer in redox reactions as well as to their beneficial influence on
376 the sensitivity of electrochemical response, the last one being influenced by the high surface area
377 to-volume ratio of this nanomaterial. Furthermore, it has been evidenced that CNTs present high
378 compatibility with other different nanomaterials and with biological compound such as enzymes
379 (Azevedo et al., 2019; Xie et al., 2019). These features qualify CNTs for electroanalytical
380 determination of target analytes in complex real samples such as biological fluids, and street
381 forensic samples.

382 However, it should be mentioned that all the special features of CNTs are not enough for high
383 electrochemical detection capacity. Their functionalization is mandatory before the use for the
384 design of electrochemical (bio)sensors, because it aims to reduce the Van der Waals and π - π
385 interactions that occur between the different tubes and that can hinder the proper interaction with
386 the target analytes (Zhang et al., 2018; Li et al., 2019).

387 **4.3.2. Strategies for carbon nanotubes immobilization at the electrode surface**

388 Although all types of CNTs are uniformly ordered, it presents major limitations due to their high
389 hydrophobicity, for example spontaneous coagulation and low solubility in aqueous solutions
390 (Putzbach and Ronkainen, 2013). To solve this shortcoming, CNTs undergo treatment with
391 concentrate solutions of acids. The most commonly used oxidative mixture consists in concentrate
392 sulphuric and nitric acids and the treatment includes refluxing and sonication steps. After this
393 oxidative treatment, defects on the surface of tubes may occur as well as their shortening. An
394 important type of defect that can be produced on both CNT walls and edges consist in the formation

395 of carboxylated sites. These functions are important because they facilitate the CNTs dispersion
396 in aqueous media and their adsorption of chemical immobilization at the electrode as a mono-layer
397 film via amidic bond formation with amine functionalities generated at the surface (Kovtyukhova
398 et al., 2003).

399 There are several studies published to date that have stated the easy functionalization of the surface
400 of CNTs (Rivas et al., 2017; Camilli, Luca, 2018; Azevedo et al., 2019; Rasheed et al., 2019). This
401 can be done both by forming covalent and non-covalent bonds with the modifying entities. A
402 suggestive example in this regard is represented by the functionalization of CNTs with organic
403 functional groups, which transforms the outer surface of the tubes to one with strong physical
404 adsorption capacity and with easily controllable surface charge (Azevedo et al., 2019).

405 The most commonly used carbon nanomaterials for modification of the working electrode surfaces
406 in voltammetry are undoubtedly CNTs. The electrocatalytic properties of CNTs were assigned to
407 their individual configuration, to some metal impurities, to the modification of their surface before
408 being used for electrode functionalization, alone or after integration in various composites. There
409 are several strategies used for the immobilization of CNT at the electrode surface, such as drop
410 coating of the homogeneous suspensions at the electrode followed by solvent evaporation or by
411 the use of CNT-based ink for printing on different planar substrates (Rezaei and Zare, 2008;
412 Trojanowicz, 2016; Hwang et al., 2019), adsorption at the electrode surface (Asturias-Arribas et
413 al., 2014; Trojanowicz, 2016), dispersion in surfactants or polymers (Lin et al., 2004), covalent
414 immobilization after functionalization with different groups (Park et al., 2011) and incorporation
415 in different composites (Gooding et al., 2003; Putzbach and Ronkainen, 2013).

416 **4.3.3. Electrochemical sensors for drugs of abuse detection based on carbon nanotubes**

417 Electrochemical sensors with CNTs have been successfully designed and have found applications
418 in different fields, such as biomedical, pharmaceutical, environmental, food, defense, forensics,
419 and many more (Trojanowicz, 2016).

420 Electrochemical sensors have found numerous applications in forensic research field, especially
421 for the direct and indirect detection and analysis of drugs of abuse. A wide range of electrode
422 platforms have been developed, including ones with CNTs to achieve increase sensitivity and
423 selectivity for targets in complex real matrix (Shaw and Dennany, 2017). Some applications of
424 CNTs in electrochemical sensing of illicit substances, adulterants and precursors are discussed
425 comparatively here, with emphasis on the advantages given by the presence of the nanomaterial
426 on the electrode surface.

427 An electrochemical sensor for cocaine based on a disposable screen-printed transducer modified
428 with MWCNTs was developed. In this case, the sensor was obtained by the physical
429 immobilization of the MWCNTs, by their simple adsorption. Firstly, the solid nanomaterial was
430 homogenous dispersed in DMF, the dispersion was dropped on the working electrode surface, and
431 then the solvent was evaporated at room temperature. This sensor allowed the selective direct
432 detection of cocaine through a voltammetric procedure even in the presence of three different
433 possible interferences that could be found in street samples, namely codeine, paracetamol and
434 caffeine (Asturias-Arribas et al., 2014).

435 In other study, linear sweep voltammetry allowed sensitive detection of cocaine in street seized
436 samples by using a glassy carbon electrode modified with MWCNT presenting $-COOH$ groups.
437 The nanomaterial was immobilized at the electrode together with β -cyclodextrin through the bonds
438 formed with the polyaniline film that was previously electrochemically generated at the electrode.
439 This is an example of low cost, rapid and simple strategy for the high reproducible and specific
440 detection of this drug that is very popular among consumers. A LOD of $1.02 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ was reported
441 for cocaine, the obtained results being confirmed with the reference method, namely high-
442 performance liquid chromatography reference method (Garrido et al., 2016).

443 Morphine was detected using an optimized square wave voltammetry (SWV) method and a carbon
444 paste electrode modified with ionic liquid and an NiO/CNTs composite. The ionic liquid chosen
445 was 1-methyl-3-butylimidazolium chloride, this element has the role of binder for the
446 nanocomposite based on CNTs. It has been observed that this nanocomposite material acts as a
447 catalyst for the electrochemical oxidation of morphine and exhibited a strong and constant electron
448 mediating effect, allowing a clear separation of the oxidation signals corresponding to morphine
449 and diclofenac. A LOD of $0.01 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ was obtained for morphine, the sensor being successfully
450 applied for the detection of morphine in a complex matrix such as human urine and pharmaceutical
451 samples (Sanati et al., 2014).

452 The same strategy, i.e. the use of carbon paste for the immobilization of the CNTs at the electrode,
453 was applied for the elaboration of an electrochemical sensor for simultaneous detection of
454 morphine and diclofenac. In this case, carbon paste was modified with vinylferrocene-
455 functionalized MWCNTs. Several electrochemical techniques were applied and SWV was chosen
456 for the evaluation of the analytical performances of the sensor. It was observed that the composite
457 electrode presented electrocatalytic effect on the electrochemical oxidation of morphine, by
458 increasing the current intensity, simultaneously with the decrease of the oxidation potential of the
459 target analyte. These properties allowed the morphine signal to be detected from that of diclofenac,
460 and implicitly their simultaneous detection in real samples with a limit of detection of 0.09 mol L^{-1}
461 1 for morphine and 2.0 mol L^{-1} diclofenac, respectively (Mokhtari et al., 2012).

462 The development of nanotechnology has allowed the miniaturization of the electrochemical cells
463 as well as of the devices necessary for their operation. Furthermore, the signal recorded at the
464 electrode can be nowadays transmitted to a Smartphone or other portable device *via* wireless or
465 Bluetooth connection, an important advantage for rapid in field testing. A number of wearable
466 sensors based on CNTs have been developed. Wearable electrochemical sensors have been
467 designed on gloves and rings for illicit substance detection.

468 Thus, a ring-based electrochemical sensor was designed for the simultaneous, direct, fast and
469 simple detection of Δ^9 -THC and alcohol in saliva by using SWV and amperometry. The dual
470 sensing ring was able to detect Δ^9 -THC by SVW and alcohol by amperometry (enzymatic
471 biosensor), with no visible interference and high sensitivity ($0.5 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ in Δ^9 -THC and 0.2 mmol
472 L^{-1} alcohol). The developed wearable dual sensor presents great perspectives for in-field roadside
473 screening for illicit substances detection and for alerting wearers about their own intoxication
474 levels before driving (Mishra et al., 2020). CNT presence makes this sensing platform a very
475 versatile one and that can be adapted for the detection of other compounds of interest including
476 other major drugs.

477 Another example refers to a rapid, on-site detection of drugs of abuse is a high relevance research
478 topic. Synthetic drugs have undergone a rapid development in the last decades, this field having a
479 continuous dynamics. This fact requires forensic researchers to quickly adapt their techniques and
480 devices to new products found on the illicit drugs market. An example of a synthetic compound
481 that has emerged in recent years is fentanyl, a synthetic opioid with very serious implications for
482 all people who come into contact with it (including those who test the confiscated evidence on the
483 street).

484 A wearable glove-based sensor has been designed for the decentralized electrochemical detection
485 of fentanyl, the sensor being placed on the glove fingertips. In this case, the flexible screen-printed
486 carbon-based electrodes were modified with a mixture of MWCNTs and 4-(3-butyl¹-imidazolio)-
487 1-butanefulfonate, which is an ionic liquid at room temperature. The optimized “lab-on-a-glove”
488 sensing system which works according to the strategy “swipe, scan, sense, and alert”, has been
489 successfully applied for the direct oxidation of fentanyl in both liquid and powder samples, a LOD
490 of 10 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ being obtained using square wave voltammetry (Barfidokht et al., 2019).

491 To summarize the use of CNTs and graphene in the detection of illicit drugs, the most relevant
492 studies in the literature sensors developments based on CNTs and graphene platforms are presented
493 in Table 3.

494 **Insert Table 3**

495 **5. Antibodies, aptamers and molecularly imprinted polymers for the detection of drugs of** 496 **abuse**

497 In the case a highly sensitive and selective detection is strived for, (bio)recognition elements such
498 as antibodies, aptamers and MIPs can be integrated in the sensor design. A few examples of
499 electrochemical sensors based on these elements are presented below.

500 Antibodies are widely used for the development of sensors for illicit drugs detection due to their
501 sensitivity and selectivity. Immunosensors offer precise analyte identification in complex matrices,
502 thanks to the highly specific antigen-antibody immunoreaction.

503 In a recent study published by Eissa *et. al.*, they implemented a multiplex immunosensor using
504 screen printed carbon array electrodes modified with gold nanoparticles for detection of morphine,
505 tetrahydrocannabinol and benzoylecgonine. Antibodies against morphine, tetrahydrocannabinol
506 and benzoylecgonine were immobilized on eight electrodes in a sensor array simultaneously, and
507 a competitive assay was used for the detection. The detection time for these three electrodes is
508 between 20-40 minutes. This method has a good selectivity and sensitivity with a detection limit
509 of 1.2 pg mL^{-1} for morphine, 7.0 pg mL^{-1} for tetrahydrocannabinol and 8.0 pg mL^{-1} for
510 benzoylecgonine. The multiplexed immunosensor was used for the detection of drugs from urine
511 samples spiked with these three drugs. Recovery percentages ranged between 88 to 115%. (Eissa
512 et al., 2019)

513 Aptamers are small (usually from 20 to 60 nucleotides) single-stranded RNA or DNA with a
514 specific three-dimensional structure. Aptamers can form complexes with the target protein to

515 inhibit its expression by blocking its activity. Currently, a large number of generated aptamers can
516 bind various targets, from inorganic molecules to large protein complex or entire cells. The main
517 advantages of aptamers are easy modification, high affinity, and good stability, and because of
518 that, they were widely used as recognition biomaterials in biosensors (Lakhin et al., 2013),(Zhang
519 and Cao), (Shen et al., 2015).

520 Aptamers are so widely applicable that new aptamer-related reports are published almost every
521 day. They are also used for drugs of abuse detection, for example a supramolecular aptamer for
522 cocaine detection were developed by Shen *et al.* In this work they used a supramolecular aptamer,
523 rolling circle amplification (RCA), and multiplex binding of a biotin-streptavidin system. The
524 aptamer fragment were assembled to a supramolecular aptamer which, in the presence of cocaine,
525 conjugates to streptavidin for anchoring of biotinylated circular DNA. They successfully detected
526 cocaine in a concentration range between 2 and 500 nmol L^{-1} with a detection limit of 1.3 nmol L^{-1}
527 (Shen et al., 2015). In another approach, Yang *at al.* implemented a novel quantitative
528 community sewage sensor for rapid and cost-effective estimation of cocaine use trends from
529 wastewater. For this study, a thiolated single-stranded DNA (ssDNA) probe was hybridized with
530 aptamer ssDNA in solution, and this step was followed by co-immobilization with 6-mercapto-
531 hexane onto the gold electrodes to control the surface density to effectively bind with cocaine.
532 They detected cocaine in a range between 10 nmol L^{-1} to 5 $\mu\text{mol } L^{-1}$ and with a LOD of 10 nmol
533 L^{-1} (Yang et al., 2016). An example of aptamer-based sensor using a nanocomposite platform
534 (MWCNT/IL/Chit) for the ultra-low (150 pmol L^{-1}) detection of cocaine was presented by
535 Roushani *et al.* (Roushani and Shahdost-fard, 2015). The approach uses riboflavin (RF) as redox
536 probe to detect cocaine in the linear range from 2 nmol L^{-1} to 2.5 $\mu\text{mol } L^{-1}$. The AgNPs-
537 functionalized aptamer was introduced to accelerate the electron transfer kinetics involved in the
538 reduction process of RF and to specifically bind the target molecule. Moreover, the same group
539 reported a similar strategy using AuNPs instead and ferricyanide as redox probe for cocaine
540 sensing (Roushani and Shahdost-Fard, 2015). This aptasensor showed an improved LOD of 100
541 pmol L^{-1} and with a linear range up to 11 $\mu\text{mol } L^{-1}$ cocaine. The applicability of the sensor was
542 tested in human blood serum and selectivity was studied against analgesic drugs.

543 MIPs are biomimetic receptors widely employed as recognition elements in the construction of
544 electrochemical sensors due to their many advantages such as low cost, simplicity in preparation,
545 stability at various temperature and pH and storage in dry state at room temperature for a long
546 time. MIPs are obtained via the molecular imprinting technique which can be done in a covalent
547 or non-covalent fashion and it involves the polymerization of monomers in the presence of the
548 template molecule (the analyte) followed by extraction of the template from the polymer matrix
549 when cavities are left behind which are complementary in size and shape with the template
550 molecule (Florea et al., 2016, 2019b).

551 A MIP based sensor for direct detection of cocaine was reported by Florea *et al.* Palladium
552 nanoparticles were firstly electrodeposited onto graphene SPE for the benefit of enhancing the
553 communication between imprinted sites and electrode and improving their homogenous
554 distribution. Then a MIP layer was synthesized by electropolymerization of *p*-aminobenzoic acid
555 (**Figure 5**). The appropriate monomer was selected via computational modelling to exhibit high
556 binding affinity for cocaine. The signal varied linearly with cocaine concentration in the range of
557 100-500 μM , with a LOD of 50 μM . The sensor was applied for the detection of cocaine in saliva
558 and river water samples with good recoveries (Florea et al., 2019a).

559 **Insert Figure 5**

560 In another study Smolinska-Kempisty *et al.* realized a potentiometric sensor for cocaine detection
561 based on molecularly imprinted polymer nanoparticles (nanoMIPs) produced by the solid-phase
562 imprinting method. MIPs are synthetic materials possessing specific binding sites able to recognize
563 a target molecule. MIPs are prepared by co-polymerization of functional monomers and a cross-
564 linker in the presence of a template molecule. In this case the functional monomer used was
565 acrylamide, because it demonstrated a highest yield and a good affinity for the target molecule. The
566 nanoparticles were incorporated in a PVC (polyvinyl chloride) matrix which was then used to
567 prepare an ion-selective membrane integrated with a potentiometric transducer. In this way the
568 nanoMIPs could detect cocaine in blood serum sample with a limit of quantification of 1 nmol L^{-1}
569 (Smolinska-Kempisty *et al.*, 2017).

570 **6. Future perspectives**

571 In the last two decades, the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC) has been
572 focusing on the worldwide safety by hindering the organized crime, corruption, terrorism and
573 drugs threats (United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime). Therefore, in the context of drugs and
574 drugs of abuse, the Laboratory and Scientific Section, Division for Policy Analysis and Public
575 Affairs developed colorimetric testing kits for rapid and simple in field identification of drugs and
576 precursors that are likely to be found in the illicit traffic. A colorimetric test is a presumptive test
577 that indicates the presence or absence of a compound. Colorimetric tests are used in-the-field as a
578 quick and cheap screening method. They are simple, sensitive and the results can be observed
579 visually. However, colorimetric tests often lack of specificity. They can be easily influenced by
580 adding certain compounds to the drug causing the test to show a false negative result. The
581 complexation with the cobalt thiocyanate in the cocaine colorimetric test could also take place in
582 the presence of other compounds, causing the test to turn blue, thus leading to a false positive
583 result. Moreover the test is influenced by temperature and the color interpretation is subjective (De
584 Jong *et al.*, 2018b). Therefore, (bio)sensing strategies in detecting drugs offer a clear advantage
585 compared to colorimetric tests, with increased selectivity and comparable analysis time.

586 Trained drug detection dogs have been used in Australia since the early 2000s. Though, due to the
587 ineffective detection strategy, dogs are more used for the deterrent effect in airports and outdoor
588 music festivals than for detection purposes (Grigg *et al.*, 2018).

589 The most commonly used strategies for the detection of illicit drugs in biological samples are
590 chromatographic and mass spectrometric methods. However, fast and sensitive determination of
591 drugs of abuse in oral fluid by techniques as Raman, infrared (IR), and nuclear magnetic resonance
592 (NMR), UV-Vis, fluorescence spectroscopy, and surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy (SERS)
593 are of high interest (D'Elia *et al.*, 2015).

594 It can be clearly seen tremendous progress in the field of disposable technology for illicit drug
595 detection due to the effort driven by the researchers in this field and law enforcement agencies.
596 For this reason, new portable technology based on instrumental techniques could step forward to
597 traditional forensic laboratory to successfully provide timely and efficient data about illicit threats.
598 Nevertheless, it is believed that their systematic use for preliminary screening would have a great

599 impact on the amount of information that could be collected during investigative processes. Point-
600 of-use instrumental techniques are more often used for screening purposes. In addition, coupling
601 the enhanced properties of nanostructured materials with the sensors in general (Hosu et al., 2019)
602 have allowed the development of simple, fast and low-cost analytical sensing methodologies for
603 illicit drugs.

604 **7. Conclusions**

605 One of the biggest challenges of our century is to develop new materials and innovative methods
606 capable to solve humanity's most stringent problems. The drugs of abuse detection in field, which
607 could have a positive impact on reducing the drug traffic is one of the challenges. Scientists are
608 making considerable efforts in solving issues related to selectivity and simultaneous detection from
609 seized samples. Nanomaterials and biomimetic elements have the capacity to improve the
610 selectivity, sensitivity and allowed the simultaneous detection. Additionally, electrochemical
611 sensors could be used in field, and could be equipped with disposable sensors avoiding the
612 contaminations.

613 This review emphasizes the latest technology based on the usage of nanomaterials and approaches
614 based on aptamers and MIPs for the detection of illicit drugs. Despite a few limitations, their
615 outcomes are very promising and could be used as field instruments to be routinely employed by
616 police and policy makers in their investigations.

617 **8. Conflict of interest**

618 *The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial*
619 *relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.*

620 **9. Author Contributions**

621 Florina Truta wrote section 3 and 5. Anca Florea wrote section 1, 2 and 5. Andreea Cernat wrote
622 section 4.1. and 4.2. Mihaela Tertis wrote section 4.3. Oana Hosu wrote section 5 and 6. Cecilia
623 Cristea did the study design, wrote section 7 and proofread the manuscript. Karolien De Wael
624 proofread the manuscript.

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637 **FIGURE 1. Metabolism of cocaine to major inactive metabolites, benzoylecgonine(BZ) and**
 638 **ecgonine methylester (EME), and to a minor active metabolite nor-cocaine (NC).**
 639 **Reproduced from Ref. (Shimomura et al., 2019).**

640

641 **FIGURE 2. Schematic representation of a (bio)sensor.**

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643

644 **FIGURE 3. The oxidation mechanism of morphine. Reproduced from Ref (Navaee et al.,**
 645 **2012).**

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649 **FIGURE 4. The principle of working of a polymer based sensor for the detection of cocaine**
650 **in presence of levamisole. Ref (Florea et al., 2018b) with permission from Talanta.**

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654 **FIGURE 5. MIP based sensor fabrication for the detection of cocaine. Reproduced from**
655 **Ref. (Florea et al., 2019a) with permission from the Royal Society of Chemistry.**

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661 **Tables**

662

663 Table 1. Overview list of (bio)sensors for drugs of abuse detection

Classes of Drugs of Abuse	Target Drugs	Type of (bio) sensor	Pretreatment	Detection Analytical method	Limit of detection (LOD) or limit of quantification (LOQ)	Samples	Ref.
Narcotics	Morphine	RGO-Pd	-	DPV	LOQ = 0.34 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ LOQ = 14 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ LOD = 0.012 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$	Human urine	(Atta et al., 2014)
		EGO-modified SPE	-	DPV	LOD = 8.77×10^{-6} $\mu\text{mol mL}^{-1}$	Urine sample	(Maccaferri et al., 2019b)
		IL/NiO/CNTCPE	-	SWV	LOD = 0.01 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ LOQ = 1.63 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$	Human urine, pharmaceutical samples	(Sanati et al., 2014)
		GNSs modified GC electrode	-	DPV	LOQ = 65 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ LOD = 0.4 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$		(Navaee et al., 2012)
	Heroin	GNSs modified GC electrode	-	DPV	LOQ = 100 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ LOD = 0.5 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$		(Navaee et al., 2012)
Stimulants	Cocaine	Supramolecular aptasensor on supramolecular aptamer, rolling circle amplification combined with multiplex binding	1.the aptamer fragments were assembled to a supramolecular aptamer, in the presence of cocaine, conjugates to streptavidin for anchoring of biotinylated circular DNA.	DPV	LOD = 0.0013 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ (at $S/N=3$) LOQ = 0.002 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$	Spiked urine Samples	(Shen et al., 2015)

of the biotin-streptavidin system for cocaine detection.	2. these modifications initiates RCA and enables sensitive electrochemical-enzymatic readout.				
SPCEs	-	SWV	LOQ = 10 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$	Street samples	(Asturias-Arribas et al., 2014)
MWCNTs-SPEs					
Aptasensor platform	Electrodeposition of thiophene macromonomer bearing polypeptides.	DPV	LOQ _{COC} = 0.0025 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ LOQ _{BE} = 0.5 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ LOD _{BE} = 0.0015 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$	Synthetic biological fluids (urine and saliva)	(Bozokalfa et al., 2016)
Pt-SPEs	Pt-SPEs was covered COHCFe	CV	LOD = 28.8 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ LOQ = 96.2 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$	Seized samples	(Balbino et al., 2016)
BDDE	-	BIA-SWV	LOQ = 0.198 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ LOD = 0.89 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$	-	(Freitas et al., 2017)
GSPE		SWV	LOD = 3 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ LOQ = 10 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$	Street samples	(De Jong et al., 2018a)
GPH-SPE	The electrodeposition of PABA and OPD	SWV	LOQ = 50 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ LOQ = 100 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$	-	(Florea et al., 2018a)

	Ultrasensitive electrochemical nanoaptasensor	1. Deposition of AuNPs on the surface of GCE 2. Covalent attachment of Apt	DPV	-	Serum	(Roushani and Shahdost-Fard, 2016)
	Potentiometric sensor based on nanoMIPs	-	-	LOQ = 0.001 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$	Blood serum sample	(Smolinska-Kempisty et al., 2017)
Methcathinone	SPEs	-	CV	LOQ = 0.098 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ (at pH=12) LOD = 0.273 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$	-	(Smith et al., 2013)
Mephedrone	SPEs	-	CV	LOQ = 0.09 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ (at pH=2) LOD = 0.224 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$	-	(Smith et al., 2013)
MEC	SPEs	-	CV	LOQ = 0.083 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ (at pH=2) LOD = 0.44 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$	-	(Smith et al., 2013)
Methcathinone	MIF	-	DPV	LOD = 0.0202 nmol mL^{-1}	Serum samples	(Zang et al., 2013)
Cathinone	MIF	-	DPV	LOD = 0.059 nmol mL^{-1}	Serum samples	(Zang et al., 2013)

MDMA	EPAD coated with ZnONRs	-	CV	LOQ= 1 $\mu\text{mol } L^{-1}$ LOD=0.1 $\mu\text{mol } L^{-1}$	Human saliva, sweat and urine.	(Narang et al., 2018)
	SPEs					
	BDD GC	-	DPV	LOD = 0.207 $\mu\text{mol } mL^{-1}$	-	(Cumba et al., 2016)
PMA	SPEs					
	BDD GC	-	DPV	LOD = 0.048 $\mu\text{mol } L^{-1}$	-	(Cumba et al., 2016)
	SPEs					
MDMA/PMA	BDD GC	-	DPV	LOD = 1.29/0.227 $\mu\text{mol } L^{-1}$	-	(Cumba et al., 2016)
	SPEs					
	SPE with NAMM	-	CA	LOQ = 79.64 $\text{nmol } mL^{-1}$	Saliva	(Wanklyn et al., 2016)
Cannabis	Δ^9 -THC					
		GC disk electrode	-30 s pre-concentration step under an applied potential of -1.2 V -The elimination of chemical interferences from samples was achieved through prior purification using the TLC technique	CV	LOD = 1.08 $\text{nmol } mL^{-1}$ LOQ = 7.64 $\text{nmol } mL^{-1}$	Hamp and hashish confiscated by the police

C-SPEs	Pt-SPEs was covered COHCFe	CV	LOD $_{\Delta^9\text{THC}}$ = 3.0 $\mu\text{mol mL}^{-1}$ LOQ $_{\Delta^9\text{THC}}$ = 9.0 $\mu\text{mol mL}^{-1}$	Seized samples	(Balbino et al., 2016)
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664 *RGO-Pd = Graphene-palladium-hybrid-modified glassy carbon electrode ; EGO-modified SPE= screen-printed electrode modified by a graphene oxide coating;*
665 *DPV=Differential pulse voltammetry; IL/NiO/CNTCPE= ionic liquid modified NiO/CNTs carbon paste electrode; SWV= square wave voltammetry; GNSs = Graphene*
666 *nanosheets; GC = glassy carbon; DDIAS= DNA-directed immobilization of aptamer sensors; MS= Mass spectrometry; SPCEs= Carbon-based SPEsScreen printed*
667 *carbon electrodes; MWCNTs-SPEs= Screen printed electrodes modified with multi wall carbon nanotubes; $\Delta^9\text{THC}$ = Δ -9-tetrahydrocannabinol; Pt-SPE = platinum*
668 *screen-printed electrode with CoHCFe = a cobalt hexacyanoferrate film; C-SPEs= carbon screen-printed electrodes; CV= cyclic voltammetry; BDDE = Boron-doped*
669 *diamond electrode; BIA-SWV= batch-injection analysis system with; GSPE= graphite screen-printed electrode; Graphite screen-printed electrodes modified with*
670 *graphene (GPH-SPE); PABA= p-Aminobenzoic acid; OPD= o-phenylenediamine; UCNPs= upconversion nanoparticles; molecularly imprinted polymer*
671 *nanoparticles (nanoMIPs); MIF= molecularly imprinted film; LC-ESI-MS/MS= liquid-chromatography-tandem-mass-spectrometry method using pneumatically*
672 *assisted electro-spray ionization; EPAD = Electrochemical paper analytical device; ZnONRs= zinc oxide nanorods; boron-doped diamond electrode (BDD); glassy*
673 *carbon electrode (GC); MDMA = 3,4-methylenedioxy-methamphetamine; para-methoxyamphetamine (PMA); SCs =Synthetic cannabinoids; QCM= quartz crystal*
674 *microbalance sensor; CE=Capillary electrophoresis; MEKC =Micellar electrokinetic chromatography; GC=Glassy carbon; CA=Chronoamperometry; MEC= 4-*
675 *Methylethcathinone; NAMM= N-(4-amino-3-methoxyphenyl)-methansufonamide*

676

677 **Table2. Limits of detection determined in live and post-mortem whole blood samples (Sørensen, 2011)**

Cathinone	LOD ($\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$)	LOD ($\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$)
	Samples from subjects	Samples collected post mortem
Norephedrine	13.22	17.85
Cathine	13.24	14.56
Ephedrine	16.36	15.15
Pseudoephedrine	17.57	18.18
Cathinone	14.09	20.8
Flephedrone	16.02	17.12
Metcathinone	8.58	12.88

Metyephedrine	13.96	12.84
Methylpseudoephedrine	7.8	8.92
Ethcathinone	8.37	7.85
Methylone	4.83	5.31
Methedrone	2.61	4.35
Mephedrone	3.95	4.51
Butylone	4.07	4.07
Amfepramone	2.43	3.41

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681 **Table 3. Overview of sensors based on graphene and CNTs platforms**

Nanomaterial	Target drug	Platform	LOD	Ref.
Graphene	Morphine	Electrochemically exfoliated graphene	8.77 nmol L ⁻¹	(Maccaferri et al., 2019a)
	Cathinone	Graphene/MIP	0.059 pmol mL ⁻¹	(Zang et al., 2013)
	Methcathinone		0.02 pmol mL ⁻¹	
	Cocaine	GO/AuNPs/aptamers	1 nmol L ⁻¹	(Jiang et al., 2012)

	Morphine	RGO/Pd	0.012 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$	(Atta et al., 2014)
	Cocaine	Magnetic graphene	1.5 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$	(Tang et al., 2011)
	Cocaine	RGO/AuNPs/Polyaniline/aptamer	0.029 nmol L^{-1}	(Hashemi et al., 2017)
	Cocaine	MWCNTs-SPE	10 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$	(Asturias-Arribas et al., 2014)
CNTs	Cocaine	MWCNTs-COOH/cyclodextrin	1.02 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$	(Garrido et al., 2016)
	Morphine	NiO/CNTs	0.01 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$	(Sanati et al., 2014)
	Morphine	MWCNTs/carbon paste	0.09 mol L^{-1}	(Mokhtari et al., 2012)
	Fentanyl	MWCNTs/4-(3-butyl-1-imidazolium)-1-butanedisulfonate	10 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$	(Barfidokht et al., 2019)

682 MIP=molecularly imprinted
 683 polymer-; RGO=reduced
 684 graphene oxide ; PdNPs=palladium nanoparticles ; GO=graphene oxide ; AuNPs=gold nanoparticles ; SPE=screen printed electrode ; MWCNTs=multiwalled carbon
 685 nanotubes.

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